

Investigating Factors Associated with Substance Use among Undergraduate Students in Tertiary Institutions in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigating factors associated with substance use among undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Ilorin metropolis using Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin as case study. The study employed 1500 self-administered questionnaires, which were distributed to students across the five institutes for filling to randomly selected participants. Data collected for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square (χ^2) test. The findings of the study showed that the prevalence of substance use/drug abuse was 36% which was a bit higher than most obtained from related previous studies. Alcohol and prescription or non-prescription of medication are mostly types of substance use/abuse. Also, the results suggest respondents seem to agree with different factors affecting the use of drugs and substance abuse. Finally, the gender, student level, student institute, the marital status and types of substance use/drug abuse were demographic characteristics associated with substance use/ drug abuse. However, other demographic characteristics that were not associated with substance use/ drug abuse according to the study included age group, place of residence, parent/guidance level of education among others.

Keywords: Undergraduate student, Tertiary Institution, Substance use, Factor, Descriptive statistics, Chi-square test.

Introduction

Substance use is an important public health concern in many countries across the globe. Among the general public, institutions of higher learning have developed a reputation for inducing new substance use among students (Blows & Isaacs, 2022). Psychoactive substances are believed to provide pleasure because they give inner peace and satisfaction, alter perception and heighten sensation (Adekeye et al., 2015). Despite its pleasurable effects, substance use has negative effects on the health, family, social, and professional life of people, making it a major public health concern (Schulte & Hser, 2013). In 2017, an estimated 271 million people of the global population, aged 15-64, had used drugs in the previous year. This is 30% higher than the 210 million reported in 2009 (United Nations, 2019). This has a high impact in terms of health consequences. The global disease burden attributable to alcohol and illicit drugs is estimated at 5.4%, while 3.7% is attributable to tobacco use alone (WHO, 2010). Globally, 585,000 people are estimated to have died as a result of drug use in 2017. The most consumed psychoactive substance globally is alcohol. However, the preferred illicit substance consumed in Africa is cannabis, while opiates are the most consumed illicit substance in Europe and Asia and cocaine predominating in South America (WHO, 2010). Life in tertiary education is a period when students transition to independence and freedom from direct supervision of their families, self-decision making, and intense academic pressure. They share living areas with strangers, form new social groups and

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305

friends, balance social engagements with academic and other life responsibilities. These expose them to certain social norms which youths uphold, which are divergent from the values they originally adopted from their parents. These perceived norms motivate the youth to indulge in unhealthy behaviors such as smoking and alcohol and drug use (Conrald et al., 2022). Some common substances used by students in tertiary institutions are: tobacco, alcohol and opioids (Gezahegn et al., 2014). Alcohol and tobacco are seen as "gateway" substances' as per the gateway drug theory; which suggests that using soft substances like cannabis, alcohol and tobacco is a behavioral doorway that leads to consumption of the so-called hard drugs like heroin, cocaine, crystal methamphetamine and ecstasy (Conrald et al., 2022).

The research work aimed at study the prevalence and risk factors associating with substance use among undergraduate students in tertiary institution in Ilorin using Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin as a case study.

Literature review

Factors affecting Drug and Substance Abuse Peer pressure is one of the key factors affecting drug and substance abuse. World Drug report indicated that drug users seek approval from their peers to join their habit as a way of seeking acceptance (Merz, 2018). Majority of the students in universities and colleges are surrounded by their peers who are experimenting for recreational purposes. This factor is further fueled by the desire to experience something unique. Nkonge (2017) found out that drug and substance abuse was more prevalent among students in third year and fourth year as compared to those in first and second year. Oluwoye (2017) found out that social media and cultural identity in drug and substance use and abuse among African and African American university students to follow musicians and rappers for fan-bases. The Hiphop genre of music with African American was found to influence the black culture. People abuse drugs and substances with most of the music videos clearly depicting the use of alcohol and cannabis sativa. Students believe that the best way to relieve the stress and forget the negative thoughts is to use drugs and substances. University students who try to balance between course workload and part time jobs are most likely rely on drugs as a coping mechanism. Despite the course work overload, part time jobs, attachments, internships, and practicums long hours, it has been noted that majority of the students in the health and science schools have more pessimistic attitudes leading them to be prone and vulnerable to drug and substance abuse (Hamdan-Mansour et al., 2017). Anxiety and uncertainties of becoming adults among majority of the students in higher learning institutions was also found to be a leading cause of the youth engaging in drug and substance abuse. Mennis et al., (2016) noted that visual exposure to these drugs and other psycho active substances either through advertisements, promotions and marketing are common at different alcohol outlets lead to craving of these substances leading to potential use and abuse. Kasundu et al., (2012) established that drug and substance abuse is rampant in many of the students who resided in private hostels outside campus. this group of students confessed to alcohol and substance abuse as compared to those who resided with their parents who came in as the second majority while the students that resided in university hostels reported the lowest levels of engaging in drug and substance abuse (Musyoka et al., 2020). The role of religion was also stated as a significant factor in drug use and substance

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abuse. Some researchers established in their findings that alcohol was commonly used in religious ceremonies among the orthodox Christians while “khat” was used for prayers among the Muslim religious leaders (Asgedom, 2017). Some of the students saw this as a way in which religious leaders are promoting the use and abuse of these substances. However, evidence-based studies have found out that majority of the students in spiritual universities are less likely to be involved in drug and substance abuse.

Material and Methods

The researcher employed 1500 self-administered questionnaires, which were distributed to students across the five institutes for filling through the class’s coordinator to randomly selected participants in May/June 2025. However, a total number of 1,416 (about 94%) returned questionnaires were thereafter analyzed. A 21 item questionnaire which comprises of three sections, namely; demographic information, factors and effect of substance use among undergraduate students, respectively was used for the survey. The reliability of the instrument was determined by a pilot test which was administered on 50 undergraduates who were not part of the sampling for the study. The Cronbach’s alpha was used to determine the internal consistency/validity of the instrument and reliability statistics of 0.875 was obtained. Data collected for the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square (χ^2) test.

The students that participated in the study were also informed and consent obtained before commencement of the study. The participants were informed that they can decline participation at any stage of the study. Privacy and confidentiality were also assured before data taken. No further approval was needed since the research did not require students’ personal identity.

Data analysis and results

Data analysis was done by statistical package for social science (SPSS v.23). Descriptive statistic were computed to study the distribution of study. Chi-square was used for categorical variables and level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

There were two age group peaks; 48.3% aged between 18 to 24 years and 21.9% aged under 18 years. There were nearly equal distributions in gender 57.3% female verses 42.7% male. There were 39.1% ND2, 21.9% ND1, 19.8% HND2 and 19.1% HND1, respectively were distribution of level of students. About 36.4% of the participants were IFMS students and 23% ICT, 21.3% IAS, 12.9% IOT and 6.5% IES students, respectively. Majority (76.5%) of the participants were single, 20.6% were married and only 3% of them were divorced/separated. Most all of the participants (70%) were from urban while 30% were rural area. About (41.9%) of the participants parent/guidance level of education were secondary, 38.1% were graduate and 20% were primary school certificate. Summary of findings is in Table 1.

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of study participants

Demographic information	Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Age group	Under 18	310	21.9
	18-24	684	48.3
	25-30	262	18.5
	31+	160	11.3
Gender	Female	811	57.3
	Male	605	42.7
Level	ND 1	310	21.9
	ND 2	554	39.1
	HND 1	271	19.1
	HND 2	281	19.8
Institute	IAS	302	21.3
	IOT	182	12.9
	IFMS	515	36.4
	IICT	325	23.0
	IES	92	6.5
Marital Status	Single	1083	76.5
	Married	291	20.6
	Divorced/separated	42	3
Place of residence	Rural	425	30
	Urban	991	70
Parent/Guidance level of education	Pry Sch. Cert.	283	20
	Secondary education	593	41.9
	Graduate	540	38.1

Out of the 1416 participants, 510 (36%) of them either using substances or abused drug while 906 (64%) were neither non users of substance nor abused drug as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Prevalence of substance use/drug abuse

Figure 2. Prevalence of types of substance use/abuse

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Figure 2 shows the types of substance either use or abuse, which was use was against the institution regulations and was not used within the institutions. 30.2% of the substance use/abuse was due to either prescription or non-prescription of medication, with 43.1% of them abuse alcohol, 5.2% abused tobacco, 6.6% use cannabis, 2.8% abused Methamphetamine, 5.3% tramadol, 1.2% use cocaine/heroin, while 5.6% may have use/abuse other substance.

Table 2. Factors affecting Substance use and drug Abuse

Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewnes s	Kurtosis
Place of residence affects drug abuse	1416	4.1	1.18	-1.27	0.51
Drug use due to previous experience	1416	3.9	1.22	-0.99	-0.22
Physiological intolerance lead to substance and drug abuse	1416	4.0	1.21	-1.12	0.15
Family background affect substance use	1416	3.9	1.22	-0.94	-0.32
The setting/area for use influence Substance use	1416	4.0	1.22	-1.06	-0.03
Substance are used to obtain desired effects	1416	4.0	1.19	-1.10	0.07
Substance use influenced by peer pressure/friends	1416	3.9	1.21	-0.95	-0.26
Misplaced priority affects substance use	1416	3.9	1.19	-1.00	-0.04
Amount of money at student disposal affect substance use	1416	3.8	1.25	-0.92	-0.35
Drugs are used to change experiences	1416	3.8	1.26	-0.88	-0.45
Moral upbringings affect use of drugs	1416	3.9	1.26	-0.99	-0.23
Overall	1416	3.9	1.22	-1.02	-0.11

From Table 2, the average mean across all the factors ranged between 3.8 – 4.1 with overall average of 3.9 \approx 4.0 which implies that the respondents seem to agree with different factors affecting the use of drugs and substance abuse. Also, in term of deviation, it’s ranging between 1.18 – 1.26 with overall deviation of 1.22 which indicates variation in terms of previous experience affecting drug and substance abuse the respondents had varying views which deviated from the mean by 3.9. This implies that on this factor ideas from the respondents not significantly differs. The values for asymmetry and kurtosis between -2 and +2 are considered acceptable in order to suggest normality of the participants’ response to substance use/drug abuse (George & Mallery, 2010; Hair et al., 2010; Kline, 2011). This implies that the participants’ response distribution does not deviate much from one another and there is equal distribution of items around the overall average.

Table 3. Demographic characteristics associated with substance use

Factor	Characteristics	Substance use or drug abuse		Total (1416)	Chi-Square Tests (p-value)
		Yes	No		
Age group	Under 18	112	198	310	0.063
	18-24	241	443	684	
	25-30	110	152	262	
	31+	47	113	160	
Gender	Female	259	552	811	0.0002
	Male	251	354	605	
Level	ND 1	104	206	310	0.0013
	ND 2	173	381	554	
	HND 1	112	159	271	
	HND 2	121	160	281	
Institute	IAS	93	209	302	0.001
	IOT	51	131	182	
	IFMS	214	301	515	
	IICT	126	199	325	
	IES	26	66	92	
Marital Status	Single	362	721	1083	0.0011
	Married	128	163	291	
	Divorced/ separated	20	22	42	
Place of residence	Rural	159	266	425	0.474
	Urban	351	640	991	
Level of education when started substance use or drug abuse	Primary Education	46	79	125	0.947
	Secondary Education	147	256	403	
	Higher Institution	317	571	888	
Parent/Guidance level of education	Pry Sch.Cert.	117	166	283	0.113
	Secondary Education	205	388	593	
	Graduate	188	352	540	
Types of substance use/drug abuse	Prescription or non-prescription medication	163	264	427	0.000
	Alcohol	243	368	611	
	Tobacco	34	39	73	
	Cannabis	20	74	94	
	Methamphetamine	10	29	39	
	Tramadol	20	55	75	
	Cocaine/Heroin	2	15	17	
Others	18	62	80		

Table 3 shows characteristics of the participants associated with substance use/drug abuse. The p-value for the gender (0.0002), student level (0.0013), student institute (0.001), the marital status (0.0011) and types of substance use/drug abuse (0.000) were statistically significant since their p-value < 0.05. This suggest that they are demographic characteristics associated with substance use/ drug abuse. Other demographic characteristics that were not associated with substance use/ drug abuse according to the study because of p-value > 0.05 included age group (0.063), place of residence (0.474), level of education when started substance use or drug abuse (0.947) and parent/guidance level of education (0.113). This implies they are not likely to determine whether or not student involve in substance use/drug abuse.

Conclusion

Based on the results from analysis, the study shows that the prevalence of substance use/drug abuse was 36% which was a bit higher than most obtained from related previous studies. Alcohol and prescription or non-prescription of medication are mostly types of substance use/abuse. Also, the results suggest respondents seem to agree with different factors affecting the use of drugs and substance abuse. Finally, the gender, student level, student institute, the marital status and types of substance use/drug abuse were demographic characteristics associated with substance use/ drug abuse. However, other demographic characteristics that were not associated with substance use/ drug abuse according to the study included age group, place of residence, parent/guidance level of education among others.

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